

SHERD SHEET

MATCH WITH OTHER CORPORA

CORPUS	WARE DESIGNATION	TYPE DESIGNATION
	Red Ware	

I. TECHNIQUE

A. HAND MADE	1. Hand Modelled	2. Coiling	3. Plate Building
	4. Core Moulding	5. Turntable (up. pt.)	6. Other
B. TURNTABLE	C. WHEELMADE	E. CASTING	

II. FABRIC

A. TEXTURE OF CLAY

GENERAL:	Coarse	Medium X	Fine
1. Pebble	2. Granule	3. Very Coarse	4. Coarse
5. Medium	6. Fine	7. Very Fine	8. Silt

B. COMPOSITION Type of Clay: Nile Alluvial

TEMPER (General):	Heavy	Medium X	Light
1. Material	Chaff	Fine sand	
2. Particle Size	fine		

C. FRACTURE COLOR

General Description	Munsell
Thin red band to reddish brown at walls	

D. HARDNESS HARD

E. POROSITY

F. TRANSVERSE STRENGTH

G. PERMEABILITY

III. SURFACE PROPERTIES

A. SURFACE TREATMENT

1. Untreated	2. Wheel Finish ?	a. ribbing	
		b. scrapped or shaved	
3. Hand Finish	a. smoothed X	b. polished by burnishing ?	c. polished by rubbing ?
	d. scrapped	e. scratched or combed	f. other
4. Coating	a. wash	b. slip	c. glaze

B. SURFACE TEXTURE Smooth

C. MECHANICAL CONDITION OF SURFACE One wall badly salt effloresced; other wall: fine horizontal ~~to~~ parallel striations

D. LUSTER	1. Matte X	2. Low	3. Medium	4. High
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E. SURFACE COLOR	General Description	CEC	Munsell
	Red Brown	D11	

IV. DECORATION

A. TECHNIQUE

1. Incised	2. Impressed	3. Gouged	4. Pinched
5. Modelled	6. Moulded	7. Painted	8. Inlaid